

Appendix D: Complete list of studies included in the Systematic Literature Review

#	Title	Authors	Publication	Identifier	Year
1	Examining the Relationship of Organizational Insiders' Psychological Capital with Information Security Threat and Coping Appraisals	A. J. Burns et al	Computers in Human Behavior (CHB)	10.1016/j.chb.2016.11.018	2017
2	Encouraging Employee Engagement With Cybersecurity: How to Tackle Cyber Fatigue	A. Reeves et al.,	SAGE Open	10.1177/21582440211000049	2021
3	The Influence of Emotions on Employees' Cybersecurity Protection_Motivation Behaviour	Abdulelah A Alshammari	Thesis, Aston University		2024
4	The Influences of Employees' Emotions on Their Cyber Security Protection Motivation Behaviour: A Theoretical Framework	Abdulelah Alshammari et al.,	International Conference on Enterprise Information Systems, ICEIS - Proceedings	10.5220/0012681600003690	2024
5	Employee responses to information security related stress: Coping and violation intention	Adel Yazdanmehr et al.,	Information Systems Journal	10.1111/isj.12417	2023
6	Exploring the Frontiers of Cybersecurity Behavior: A Systematic Review of Studies and Theories	Afrah Almansoori	Applied Sciences (Switzerland)-MPDI	10.3390/app13095700	2023
7	The effect of resilience and job stress on information security awareness	Agata McCormac et al.,	Information and Computer Security	10.1108/ICS-03-2018-0032	2018
8	Going Beyond Deterrence: A Middle-Range Theory of Motives and Controls for Insider Computer Abuse	AJ Burns et al.,	Information Systems Research (ISR)	10.2139/ssrn.4079801	2022
9	The Adaptive Roles of Positive and Negative Emotions in Organizational Insiders' Engagement in Security-Based Precaution Taking	Alan J. Burns et al.,	Information Systems Research	10.1287/isre.2019.0860	2019
10	Leveraging human factors in cybersecurity: an integrated methodological approach	Alessandro Pollini et al.,	Cognition, Technology & Work	10.1007/s10111-021-00683-y	2021
11	Reliability, Validity, and Strength of a Unified Model for Information Security Policy Compliance	Alex Koohang et al.,	Journal of Computer Information Systems	10.1080/08874417.2020.1779151	2020
12	Beyond Fear and Frustration - Towards a Holistic Understanding of Emotions in Cybersecurity	Alexandra von Preuschen et al.,	Proceedings of the Twentieth Symposium on Usable Privacy and Security	10.3929/ethz-b-000669758	2024
13	How do you Feel about Cybersecurity? – A Literature Review on Emotions in Cybersecurity	Alexandra von Preuschen et al.,	Proceedings of the International Symposium on Technikpsychologie	10.2478/9788366675896-001	2023
14	Determinants of Information Security Awareness and Behaviour Strategies in Public Sector Organizations among Employees	Al-Shanfari I et al.,	International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications,	10.14569/IJACSA.2022.0130855	2022

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15	A Framework for an Effective Information Security Awareness Program in Healthcare A Case Study of Computer Game in Hospital Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia	Arash Ghazvini et al.,	IJACSA) International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications	10.14569/IJACSA.2017.080226	2017
16	Stress, Burnout, and Security Fatigue in Cybersecurity: A Human Factors Problem	Calvin Nobles	HOLISTICA – Journal of Business and Public Administration	10.2478/hjbpa-2022-0003	2022
17	Towards Diagnosing and Mitigating Behavioral Cyber Risks	Carlo Pugnetti et al.,	Risks-MDPI	10.3390/risks12070116	2024
18	Working Conditions and Cybersecurity: Time Pressure, Autonomy and Threat Appraisal Shaping Employees' Security Behavior	Cornelia Gerdenitsch et al.,	Cyberpsychology: Journal of Psychosocial Research on Cyberspace	10.5817/CP2023-4-7	2023
19	The Impact of an Employee's Psychological Contract Breach on Compliance with Information Security Policies: Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation	Daeun Lee et al.,	Cognition, Technology & Work	10.1007/s10111-023-00727-5	2023
20	Your Hospital Needs You: Eliciting Positive Cybersecurity Behaviours from Healthcare Staff	Dawn Branley-Bell et al.,	Annals of Disaster Risk Science	10.51381/adrs.v3i1.51	2020
21	Cyber Security in Hospitals: A Network-Oriented Model for Behavioural Learning of Employees During Phishing Simulations	Debby Bouma et al.,	15th International Conference on European Transnational Education (ICEUTE 2024), Springer	10.1007/978-3-031-75016-8_10	2025
22	From awareness to action: Designing effective cybersecurity training programs	Diana Ussher-Eke et al.,	International Journal of Science and Research Archive	10.30574/ijrsra.2025.16.2.2348	2025
23	Structural Model of the Healthcare Information Security Behavior of Nurses Applying Protection Motivation Theory	EunWon Lee et al.,	International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health	10.3390/ijerph18042084	2021
24	Emotionally and Socially Aware Approaches to Understanding and Changing Users' Cybersecurity Behavior	Fagan, Michael et al.,	Thesis- University of Connecticut		2017
25	Anger or Fear? Effects of Discrete Emotions on Employee's Computer-Related Deviant Behavior	Feng Xu et al.,	Information & Management	10.1016/j.im.2019.103180	2020
26	Digital detox_ exploring the impact of cybersecurity fatigue	Filiz Mizrak et al.,	Discover Mental Health	10.1007/s44192-025-00149-x	2025
27	The Mediating Role of Psychological Empowerment in Information Security Compliance Intentions	Gurpreet Dhillon et al.,	Journal of the Association for Information Systems	10.17705/1jais.00595	2020

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28	Examining the factors affecting users' cybersecurity behaviour in mobile payment contactless technologies: A hybrid SEM-ANN approach	Hana Yousuf Zainal et al.,	Thesis, The British University in Dubai		2022
29	Understanding employees' information security-related stress and policy compliance intention: the roles of information security fatigue and psychological capital	Hao Chen et al.,	Information and Computer Security	10.1108/ICS-03-2022-0047	2022
30	What users do besides problem-focused coping when facing it security threats: An emotion-focused coping perspective	Huigang Liang and Yajiong Xue	MIS Quarterly: Management Information SystemsMIS Quarterly	10.25300/MISQ/2019/14360	2019
31	Cybersecurity Training in the Healthcare Domain	Ilkka Tikanmäki et al.,	The Proceedings of the 24th European Conference on Cyber Warfare and Security	10.34190/eccws.24.1.3377	2025
32	Psychological Profiling for Enhancing Cybersecurity Training Effectiveness in Educational Institutions	Jamila Djumabaeva et al.,	Journal of Internet Services and Information Security	10.58346/jisis.2025.i2.063	2025
33	Fortifying healthcare: An action research approach to developing an effective SETA program	Jason A. Williams et al.,	Computers and Security	10.1016/j.cose.2023.103655	2024
34	Positive emotions and employees' protection-motivated behaviours: a moderated mediation model	Jie Zhen et al.,	Journal of Business Economics and Management	10.3846/jbem.2020.13169	2020
35	Impact of negative emotions on violations of information security policy and possible mitigations	Jie Zhen et al.,	Behaviour and Information Technology	10.1080/0144929X.2021.1921029	2022
36	Assessing the role of emotional intelligence in risk behavior across safety critical environments: A systematic review	Joel Samu.,	Transportation Research Interdisciplinary Perspectives	10.1016/j.trip.2025.101627	2025
37	Costly but effective: Comparing the factors that influence employee anti-malware behaviours	John Blythe et al.,	Computers in Human Behavior	10.1016/j.chb.2018.05.023	2018
38	Predicting Employee Information Security Policy Compliance On A Daily Basis: The Interplay Of Security-Related Stress, Emotions, And Neutralization	John D'arcy Et Al.,	Information and Management	10.1016/j.im.2019.02.006	2019
39	Cognitive-affective drivers of employees' daily compliance with information security policies: A multilevel, longitudinal study	John D'Arcy et al.,	Information Systems Journal	10.1111/isj.12173	2017

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40	Enhancing users' security engagement through cultivating commitment the role of psychological needs fulfilment	Joshua Davis et al.,	European Journal of Information Systems	10.1080/0960085X.2021.1927866	2021
41	A systematic review of current cybersecurity training methods	Julia Prümmer et al.,	Computers and Security	10.1016/j.cose.2023.103585	2024
42	Human factors in cybersecurity: an interdisciplinary review and framework proposal	Kalam Khadka	International Journal of Information Security	10.1007/s10207-025-01032-0	2025
43	The Importance of Conceptualising the Human-Centric Approach in Maintaining and Promoting Cybersecurity-Hygiene in Healthcare 4.0	Kioskli, Kitty et al.,	Applied Sciences (Switzerland)-MPDI	10.3390/app13063410	2023
44	The Role of the Organization in Promoting Information Security-Related Behavior Among Resident Physicians in Hospitals in Germany: Cross-Sectional Questionnaire Study	Kraushaar & Bohnet-Joschko	Journal of Medical Internet Research	10.2196/46257	2025
45	Hospital Staff's Adherence to Information Security Policy: A Quest for the Antecedents of Deterrence Variables	Kuang-Ming Kuo	INQUIRY , Sage	10.1177/00469580211029599	2021
46	The Employee Cybersecurity Awareness Framework	Laura M. Bishop et al.,	Human Behavior and Emerging Technologies	10.1155/hbe2/1025045	2025
47	The Impact of Challenge Information Security Stress on Information Security Policy Compliance: The Mediating Roles of Emotions	Lin Chen et al.,	Psychology Research and Behavior Management	10.2147/PRBM.S359277	2022
48	Exploring the Influence of Direct and Indirect Factors on Information Security Policy Compliance_SLR	Mada Alassaf et al.,	IEEE Access	10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3132574	2021
49	Behavioral responses to a cyber attack in a hospital environment	Markus Willing et al.,	Scientific Reports	10.1038/s41598-021-98576-7	2021
50	Evaluating Staff Attitudes, Intentions, and Behaviors Related to Cyber Security in Large Australian Health Care Environments: Mixed Methods Study	Martin Dart et al.,	JMIR Human Factors	10.2196/48220	2023
51	Factors influencing the intention to comply with data protection regulations in hospitals: based on gender differences in behavior and deterrence	Michael Foth	European Journal of Information Systems	10.1057/ejis.2015.9	2015

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52	How can hospitals better protect the privacy of electronic medical records? Perspectives from staff members of health information management departments	Ming-Ling Sher	Health Information Management Journal	DOI: 10.1177/1833358316671264	2016
53	Why Employees (Still) Click on Phishing Links: Investigation in Hospitals	Mohammad S Jalali et al.,	JOURNAL OF MEDICAL INTERNET RESEARCH	10.2196/16775	2020
54	Gender Difference and Employees' Cybersecurity Behaviors	Mohd Anwar	Computers in Human Behavior	10.1016/j.chb.2016.12.040	2017
55	From awareness to influence: toward a model for improving employees' security behaviour	Moneer Alshaikh	Personal and Ubiquitous Computing	10.1007/s00779-021-01551-2	2021
56	Toward a unified model of information security policy compliance	Moody, Gregory D.	MIS Quarterly: Management Information Systems	10.25300/MISQ/2018/13853	2018
57	Examining the Link Between Stress Level and Cybersecurity Practices of Hospital Staff in Indonesia	Muhammad Ali Fauzi et al.,	Proceedings of the 16th International Conference on Availability, Reliability and Security	10.1145/3465481.3470094	2021
58	The cybersecurity behavioral research: A tertiary study	Naurin Farooq Khan	Computers and Security	10.1016/j.cose.2022.102826	2022
59	A Replication Study of User Motivation in Protecting Information Security using Protection Motivation Theory and Self Determination Theory	Ning Yang	Transactions on Replication Research	10.17705/1atrr.00053	2020
60	Cybersecurity Behavior among Government Employees: The Role of Protection Motivation Theory and Responsibility in Mitigating Cyberattacks	Noor Suhani Sulaiman	Information (Switzerland) - MDPI	10.3390/info13090413	2022
61	Indirect effect of management support on users' compliance behaviour towards information security policies	Norshima Humaidi	Health Information Management Journal	10.1177/1833358317700255	2017
62	Examining the Differential Effectiveness of Fear Appeals in Information Security Management Using Two-Stage Meta-Analysis	Paul Benjamin Lowry et al.,	Journal of Management Information Systems	10.1080/07421222.2023.2267318	2023
63	Reliable Behavioural Factors in the Information Security Context	Peter Mayer	Proceedings of ARES '17, Reggio Calabria, Italy, August 29-September 01, 2017	10.1145/3098954.3098986	2017
64	The Impact of Collectivism and Psychological Ownership on Protection Motivation: A Cross-Cultural Examination	Philip Menard et al.,	Computers & Security	10.1016/j.cose.2018.01.020	2018
65	The Impact of Organizational Commitment on Insiders' Motivation to Protect Organizational Information Assets	Posey, Clay et al.,	Journal of Management Information Systems	10.1080/07421222.2015.1138374	2015

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66	Effects of Organization Insiders' Self-Control and Relevant Knowledge on Participation in Information Systems Security	Princely Ifinedo	SIGMIS-CPR 2017 - Proceedings of the 2017 ACM SIGMIS Conference on Computers and People Research	10.1145/3084381.3084384	2017
67	Roles of Organizational Climate, Bonds, and Perceptions of Security Threats on IS Security Policy Compliance Intentions	Princely Ifinedo	Information Resources Management Journal	10.4018/IRMJ.2018010103	2018
68	Mapping the Psychosocialcultural Aspects of Healthcare Professionals' Information Security Practices: Systematic Mapping Study	Prosper Kandabongee Yeng et al.,	JMIR Human Factors	10.2196/17604	2021
69	A Framework for Assessing Motivational Methods Towards Incentivizing Cybersecurity Practice in Healthcare	Prosper Kandabongee Yeng, et al.,	7th International Conference on Sustainable Information Engineering and Technology 2022 (SIET '22) ACM	10.1145/3568231.3568285	2022
70	Investigation into Phishing Risk Behaviour among Healthcare Staff	Prosper Kandabongee Yeng, et al.,	Information (Switzerland) - MDPI	10.3390/info13080392	2022
71	Assessing the effect of human factors in healthcare cyber security practice: An empirical study	Prosper Kandabongee Yeng, et al.,	PCI '21: Proceedings of the 25th Pan-Hellenic Conference on Informatics	10.1145/3503823.3503909	2021
72	Can the Cognitive Dissonance (CD) concept help to mitigate phishing susceptibility in healthcare?	Prosper Kandabongee Yeng, et al.,	Journal of Medical Internet Research	10.2196/preprints.68051	2024
73	A Comprehensive Assessment of Human Factors in Cyber Security Compliance toward Enhancing the Security Practice of Healthcare Staff in Paperless Hospitals	Prosper Yeng et al.,	Information (Switzerland) - MPDI	10.3390/info13070335	2022
74	Information Security Behavior in Health Information Systems: A Review of Research Trends and Antecedent Factors	Puspita Kencana Sari et al.,	Healthcare (Switzerland) - MDPI	10.3390/healthcare10122531	2022
75	Review and insight on the behavioral aspects of cybersecurity	Rachid Ait Maalem Lahcen	Cybersecurity	10.1186/s42400-020-00050-w	2020
76	Onlooker effect and affective responses in information security violation mitigation	Sahar Farshadkhah et al.,	Computers & Security	10.1016/j.cose.2020.102082	2021
77	Emotional Experiences of Cybersecurity Breach Victims	Sanja Budimir	Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking	10.1089/cyber.2020.0525	2021
78	We Are Not Equipped to Identify the First Signs of Cyber-Physical Attacks: Emotional Reactions to Cybersecurity Breaches on Domestic Internet of Things Devices	Sanja Budimir	Applied Sciences (Switzerland)-MPDI	10.3390/app142411855	2024
79	Emotional Reactions to Cybersecurity Breach Situations: Scenario-Based Survey Study	Sanja Budimir	Journal of Medical Internet Research	10.2196/24879	2021

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80	Victim's Negative Emotion Processes In Cybersecurity Breach Situations: A Testimony of Anger and Fear-Related Emotion Processes	Sanja Budimir et al.,	SSRN Electronic Journal	10.2139/ssrn.4101947	2022
81	Understanding security behaviour among healthcare professionals by comparing results from technology threat avoidance theory and protection motivation theory	Sanjana Sundara Raj Sreenath, et al.,	Behaviour and Information Technology- Taylor and Francis	10.1080/0144929X.2024.2314255	2024
82	Coping with Information Security Stressors in Healthcare	Savoli, Azadeh et al.,	Twenty-third Americas Conference on Information Systems		2017
83	What Do Systems Users Have to Fear Using Fear Appeals to Engender Threats and Fear	Scott R. Boss	MIS Quarterly	10.25300/MISQ/2015/39.4.5	2015
84	Influence of Human Factors on Cyber Security within Healthcare Organisations: A Systematic Review.	Sokratis Nifakos et al.,	MDPI Sensors	10.3390/s21155119	2021
85	Theory-Based Model and Prediction Analysis of Information Security Compliance Behavior in the Saudi Healthcare Sector	Sultan T. Alanazi	Symmetry -MDPI	10.3390/SYM12091544	2020
86	Driving behaviour change with cybersecurity awareness	Sunil Chaudhary	Computers and Security	10.1016/j.cose.2024.103858	2024
87	Developing metrics to assess the effectiveness of cybersecurity awareness program	Sunil Chaudhary	Journal of cybersecurity	10.1093/cybsec/tyac006	2022
88	The Theory of Planned Behavior and Information Security Policy Compliance	Teodor Sommestad et al.,	Journal of Computer Information Systems	10.1080/08874417.2017.1368421	2017
89	"No point worrying" – The role of Threat Devaluation in Information Security Behavior	Thompson, Nik et al.,	Computers and Security	10.1016/j.cose.2024.103897	2024
90	Establishing a Model for the User Acceptance of Cybersecurity Training	Wesam Fallatah et al.,	Future Internet - MDPI	10.3390/fi16080294	2024
91	Beyond Deterrence A Systematic Review of the Role of Autonomous Motivation in Organizational Security Behavior studies	Xiaowei Chen	CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI '25)	10.1145/3706598.3713122	2025
92	It ain't my business: a coping perspective on employee effortful security behavior	Zhengchuan Xu et al.,	Journal of Enterprise Information Management	0.1108/JEIM-10-2018-0229	2019